

Developments in the Field of Neurosurgery

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Abstract: *This article discusses the development, modern technologies, and the future of neurosurgery. It also provides information about clinical examination, including its plan. Modern technologies in the future will help to develop and improve the quality of examinations and operations in the field of neurosurgery, as well as reduce the number of fatal outcomes.*

Keywords: *neurosurgery, neurologist, radiologist, physiologist, resuscitator, microfluidic technology, neuromapping techniques, kinetic implants, MRI.*

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Neurosurgery is a section of medicine that uses surgical methods for treating diseases of the central and peripheral nervous system.

Neurosurgeons always work as part of a large team, which includes anesthesiologists, resuscitators, neurologists, radiologists, ophthalmologists, otoneurologists, physiologists, radiologists, chemotherapists, pathologists and, if necessary, representatives of other medical specialties.

Moreover, in some cases, neurosurgical intervention is only one, and not the most important, stage of the patient's comprehensive treatment.

History of neurosurgery

The separation of neurosurgery into a separate medical specialty occurred at the turn of the 19th and 20th centuries, but its roots go back to ancient times. The most ancient skulls with traces of trepanation date back to 12-10 thousand years BC, in the Peruvian necropolis left over from the Inca civilization (2000 years BC) about 10% of the skulls have traces of trepanation, and the nature of the bone changes indicates that most patients successfully underwent surgery.

RESEARCH METHODS IN NEUROSURGERY

Examination of a patient in neurosurgery, as in any other clinical discipline, begins with collecting complaints, anamnesis of the current disease, and clarification of the patient's medical history. Then an examination is carried out with an assessment of the condition of all organs and systems; if pathology is detected, an in-depth study is carried out, if necessary, with the involvement of specialists in related fields and additional studies.

CLINICAL EXAMINATION

A routine neurological examination includes:

- assessment of the level of consciousness;
- examination of meningeal signs;
- assessment of the patient's mental state;
- determination of the dominant hemisphere;
- assessment of the function of the cranial nerves on both sides;
- assessment of the motor sphere;
- assessment of sensitivity;
- assessment of coordination, statics and gait;
- assessment of pelvic functions;
- presence of paroxysmal symptoms;
- assessment of the patient's condition according to the Karnofsky scale.

Modern technologies in neurosurgery

Neural devices that restore motor functions in paralysis provide control over prostheses or the resumption of various neurological processes in the brain. Neuromapping techniques make it possible to identify and preserve key areas of brain function. With the use of innovative direct

brain-computer communication systems, retraining of motor skills with restoration of control over paralyzed limbs becomes possible for people who have suffered a stroke.

High-power laser technologies under magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) control are used in the treatment of inoperable brain tumors. New osteogenic materials significantly accelerate the healing process in spinal and orthopedic surgeries. Endovascular methods with minimal invasion provide effective removal of blood clots in the vascular system. Microfluidic technology allows for the pinpoint isolation of lymphocytes, which serves as an advanced tool for both the diagnosis and treatment of cancer. Modern kinetic implants minimize the risk of tissue proliferation and blockage of cerebrospinal fluid shunts. Brain-computer interaction technologies are used to treat chronic pain, and neuromodulation methods are aimed at correcting metabolic processes and treating long-term diseases.

The future of neurosurgery

The development of technology continues to open up new possibilities. Artificial intelligence is already being used to analyze medical images, helping doctors more accurately diagnose tumors and plan surgeries. Genetics and molecular biology also play a key role in understanding the nature of certain diseases, which opens the door to new treatments.

Another promising area is regenerative medicine.

Research in the field of stem cells shows that in the future it will be possible to restore damaged nerve tissue. In addition, neurostimulation methods are actively developing, which can be used to treat diseases such as Parkinson's disease, depression and chronic pain.

Conclusion

Neurosurgery is a field of medicine that is at the forefront of science and technology. Surgeons face incredibly complex challenges every day, saving lives and giving people hope for a full life. Thanks

to the efforts of doctors, scientists and engineers, neurosurgery continues to develop, offering new treatments and improving the quality of life of patients.

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